

Equality, Justice and Harmony

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A STUDY ON INDIAN MEN

BIAS BY BIRTH

DISCRIMINATION AGAINST MEN

AUTHOR: RUDOLPH DSOUZA

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MyNation Hope Foundation(INDIA)

Reg : S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn., New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212 / +91-9900954101

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Summary: Study on discrimination against Men covers a broad range of research on men's health and wellbeing. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. There is widespread discrimination towards men in every wake of life since birth, especially in India because of government policies. This article is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by international organizations as well as government bodies within India.

Key Findings: The majority of men feel shy to come forward to report discrimination, abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports of discrimination on men or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular.

Methodology: Information for this report is sourced from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), various secondary sources, medical journals, and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics, etc.

Introduction: There is no research data available on discrimination against Men nor are any Studies on their mental health recorded in any existing scientific literature. Any discrimination or bias on men affects their lives physically, mentally, emotionally, and psychologically. It is also a violation of basic human rights. Most of the discrimination on men is however unreported, unnoticed or simply ignored which may lead to denial in acceptance by their families, to divorce or depression, and even to suicide in extreme cases.

Abused and discriminated men often are victimized or side lined at early stage of their life or during childhood. However many men also think that, for reasons of

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masculinity, they have no other option than silently suffer because most of the abuse and discrimination comes from their own kind.

Abused men are also more restrained than women in revealing their victimization partly for fear of being ridiculed and shamed. Many of the men had never even told close family members about the abuse. Men think expressing or fighting back discrimination makes them more vulnerable. Shame and fear of being ridiculed force men to keep their problems hidden, adding to this the societal views of proper masculine behaviour. Lack of support and resources has also ensured that the most shocking form of discrimination on men have remained hidden till date.

The long lasting negative effects are seen to persist in those who are the bread winner for their family. The psychological harm visited upon men victimized by the society tends to contradict those who subscribe to the view that abused men do not suffer psychologically. Indeed, when the issue of psychological harm was examined, empirically, findings revealed no significant gender differences in psychosomatic illness or stress. Discrimination in everyday life forces men to live depressed and die early.

As far as men are concerned, no studies have addressed the repercussions of experiences of discrimination on men's health. All over the world, this issue is not a specific priority for research and overshadows the fact that men may also be badly impacted by such discrimination.

There may be many reasons including socio-economic, societal influences as well as consistent failure of the government to provide help when needed. These however can be dealt with provided that such men get all the required help and support so as to change and improve their way of life.

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Society Vs. Men

No man is born a criminal. Society around makes him what he is. Society includes everyone around him. Family dependencies, social and economic deprivation of basic needs are also key factors. It starts from the initial days of upbringing with good education, a supporting family, healthy public environment, societal emphasis on ethics and values of the family system and nurturing good habits for physical and mental health, all playing important roles. But discrimination or bias towards men is not common in today's world. Because of masculinity, society considers only women suffer as they term women as weaker sex.

In the modern e-linked world, media content on TV, internet and print media are also important factors with any access to improper content having a devastating effect on immature children and teenagers. Women have all out support from everyone, but man has none.

This study has been conducted in India and on Indian Men only. As per the study of MyNation, in India despite there being no governmental support (like there is for women) majority of men try to survive by whatever means possible, struggling to make ends meet without engaging in any criminal activities. Majority of men travel to distant cities for employment and commute long distances only for better pay, often surviving on only one meal per day to keep their dependents happy. 95% of men and only 5% of women contribute or support families economically and financially to ensure proper meals and nutrition for their families. Society considers that it is the man's duty to pay all bills and women are excused.

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Women Vs. Men

Most of the criminal codes (IPC/Cr.P.C) in India are blatantly biased in favour of women. Many of the special acts created for the welfare of women are drafted not actually for women but for appeasement of the feminist lobby. Quite often such acts are poorly drafted and deliberately kept wide open to misinterpretation, being totally biased and favoring women in general and thus are tailor made to abuse and misuse by disgruntled and vindictive women.

These half-baked drafts are publicly supported and intensely lobbied by feminist mafia and so in double quick time they become the law of the land without delving deep into the possible consequences. Most of such acts and amendments are introduced very quickly without taking proper measures for society to adapt to the same. They lack any clarity and appear to be created with the single motive of multiplying litigation in the country. There being little doubt but most regrettably such a result would always be welcomed by the legal fraternity, police and supporting departments.

With a country having 50% women population no government is brave enough to challenge such notions. As a matter of fact those who insist either on denying or repudiating countless, empirically sound studies showing women to be no less violent than men, act in a manner very similar to those who once vehemently insisted that the earth was flat and who then went on to brand the purveyors of new knowledge as heretics. But it is not just that the idea of women's complicity in interpersonal or intimate violence challenges the old ideas and what many regard as common sense, it also generates fear among those with vested interests in the perpetuation of government funding and other undeserved benefits based on the age old notion that spousal violence is a wholly male-perpetrated phenomenon.

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Also it is perceived by some feminist chauvinists as undercutting of their power derived solely from the presentation of women only as helpless victims, a notion that leads uninformed and well-meaning sponsors to fund women's services (but not people's services), and to enact legislation, such as the *Prevention of Domestic Violence Act Against Women (PWDVA)*, that empowers only one gender i.e. women, but not people overall. Consequently, the notion that women are no less violent than men is very threatening to those wishing to empower only one gender at the expense of the other gender, particularly given the fact that there is virtually no data demonstrating that government-funded feminist approaches or organizations such as the *National Commission of Women* have been effective in resolving issues of domestic violence.

There is a women behind every crime listed above, either she is involved directly abusing/abetting or killing a man or is the reason for the crime. In India, Women are empowered to kill anyone and most of the time she escapes punishment because of the biased Indian laws which are favourable to Women and encourage them to take the lead in a crime. She will get away even though she is abetting the suicide of a man and even if she is charged, she will hardly be sentenced for 2/3 years. But if a man is convicted, he will get a life in prison which shows how the Indian Judiciary is biased.

(CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>)

Abused Male victims tend to find that exiting an abusive situation is especially difficult. Male victims believe that it is their responsibility to provide for their children and in many cases they act as actual shields or buffers between their wives and their children to protect the latter, sometimes even becoming the targets of physical aggression that otherwise would have been directed towards

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their children. Many of the men also strongly believed that no matter how much their partners abused them, that the judicial system would always rule against them. Thus not only would they fail to gain custody of their children if they left the marital relationship but visitation also would be blocked by their wives as a continuation of controlling and abusive behaviour, with husbands having little or no recourse under the law.

There may be multiple reasons for committing crimes including socio-economic, and societal influence, as well as failure of government to provide minimum help for men in need, however petty crimes can be prevented if men can get the required help and support in time to change their way of life thus stopping them from becoming criminals.

As per the study of MyNation conducted in India and on Indian Men only, there is no government provided support for men. Although the Government of India has come out with many schemes and plans, none have been created to deal with the challenges and problems faced exclusively by Men in India. In contrast there is a multitude of various Government of India schemes for women as listed below.

1. Mother and Child Tracking System (MCTS)
2. Pradhan Mantri Matritva Vandana Yojana
3. Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls –
 - a. Sabla Rashtriya Mahila Kosh
4. National Action Plan for Children
5. Digital Laado (Digital Laado) –
 - a. Giving Digital Wings to Daughters Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme
6. One Stop Centre Scheme
 - a. Emergency Response and Rescue Services
 - b. Medical assistance
 - c. Assistance in lodging FIR /NCR/DIR
 - d. Psycho - social support/ counselling
 - e. Legal aid and counselling

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- f. Shelter
- g. Video Conferencing Facility to record statement for police/ courts
- 7. Women Helpline Scheme (24 Hours)
- 8. UJJAWALA: A Comprehensive Scheme for Prevention of trafficking and Rescue, Rehabilitation and Re-integration of Victims of Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation Working Women Hostel
- 9. Ministry approves new projects under Ujjawala Scheme and continues existing projects SWADHAR Greh (A Scheme for Women in Difficult Circumstances)
- 10. Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women (STEP)
- 11. NARI SHAKTI PURASKAR
- 12. Awardees of Stree Shakti Puruskar, 2014 & Awardees of Nari Shakti Puruskar
- 13. Awardees of Rajya Mahila Samman & Zila Mahila Samman
- 14. Mahila police Volunteers
- 15. Mahila E-Haat
- 16. Mahila Shakti Kendras (MSK)
- 17. NIRBHAYA

Different schemes for women in the State of Goa:

Kanyadhan Scheme

This Scheme provide immediate financial assistance of Rs.25000 to the economically weaker section of the society for their daughter's marriage thereby achieving a goal of upliftment of the down trodden.

Mamta Scheme

This scheme provides financial incentives of Rs.5000 to mother who delivers a female child.

Dhanalaxmi Scheme

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Under this scheme the Government provide Rs.25000 in the form of fixed deposit in the name of newly born girl child which can be accessed by the girl on completing 18 year of age. The scheme aims at improving the sex ratio of girl child in Goa.

Yashaswini Scheme

This scheme aims to promote self-help group for self-employment. The state social welfare board will provide financial assistance to each self-help group to the tune of Rs.1 lakh.

Shelter home for women

This scheme has been implemented to provide temporary shelter and support to those women who have no family or social support. It aims to rehabilitate the women socially and economically by provision of skill training.

Grih Adhar Scheme

Goa Government provides Rs.1000 per month to those housewives whose family's gross income is less than 300000 per annum. The scheme is introduced to off-set the impact created due to price rise.

From Government of Haryana : Swayamsidha, Swa-Shakti, Balika Samridhi, Hostel for working women, Swadhar, Kishori Shakti Yojana, Ladli.

Kanyashree Prakalpa from Government of West Bengal

This scheme is implemented by the Department of Women Development and Social Welfare, Government of West Bengal in the form of conditional cash transfers.

The Kanyashree scholarship is Rs.750 annually for girls between the age of 13 and 18 years along with a one-time grant of Rs. 25,000 for girls between the ages of 18 and 19 years.

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Mazi Kanya Bhagyashree Scheme from Government of Maharashtra

The girl child's mother receives Rs.5000 every year for the first 5 years after the birth of the girl child. Subsequently, financial aid of Rs.2500 per year is provided till the girl child is enrolled in 5th class.

After this, the financial aid is increased to Rs.3000 per year till the girl child is enrolled in class 12. Once she attains the age of 18 years, she will receive Rs.1lakh annually for her education. Further payouts may be available to the girl child for further studies.

Bhagyashree Scheme of Karnataka government

The girl child receives health insurance cover up to a maximum of Rs. 25,000 annually. The girl child receives an annual scholarship of Rs.300 to Rs.1000 up to class 10th.

Ladli Laxmi Yojana of Madhya Pradesh

Rs.6000 worth of National Saving Certificates will be purchased every year for the first 5 years in the name of the beneficiary.

Out of this investment, Rs.2000 will be invested after the girl child is admitted in 6th class and subsequently Rs.4000 will be invested in the admission of a girl in 9th class.

This is just a quickly compiled list of various support schemes available for women which highlights the gender biased approach of the governments and completely exposes it's hypocrisy in crying foul over the high crime rate by men while doing absolutely nothing to alleviate the same.

Other than above Government sponsored schemes, there are other perks sponsored by State / Organizations and Individuals.

Free Bicycle to Girl child

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Education seat reservation quota for girls.

Transport seats Reservation.

Ladies only Bus/Train

Women only queue

Free Bus ride in Delhi

Free Legal Assistance/Aid

Fee PIL

In fact men are burdened by the very notions of 'Patriarchy' that feminists are so fond of attacking daily. The unjust burden so imposed on men leads them to take the heavy responsibility of the entire family which may extend to distant relatives and cover even two or sometimes three generations. Driven by notions of being the sole provider and having no support at all from the government nor from society at large, men may feel that they have no option other than to engage in criminal activity. Once apprehended neither the law enforcement nor the judicial authorities make any attempt to understand the critical circumstances that may have driven a man to commit a crime. Here too the contrast in society's hypocrisy while perceiving an accused becomes apparent as any woman committing a crime is immediately excused by claiming 'depression' or 'dispute with husband' or 'abuse' but no such reasoning is ever attempted in case of a man accused of a crime. Noteworthy is the fact that though Patriarchy is the evil that all gynocentric laws claim to be fighting against, no laws have ever been made to assist men burdened with the very same concept of Patriarchy and indeed no mention is ever made of the same by law makers nor by law enforcement nor even by the judiciary. In such a situation men feel absolutely helpless and desperate which may drive at least some men to turn to a life of crime.

There is another aspect also that is relevant here. The idea that women are the weaker sex is so deeply ingrained in the psyche of human beings that even when it comes to sentencing it is men who quite often get sentenced to longer sentences and who in general will face harsher penalties as compared to women quite often for committing the same crime. Longer sentences leading to greater

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exposure to criminal influences increases the possibility of a man turning into a full-fledged criminal when in fact had he been a woman he would stand a good chance of never going to prison in the first place.

It looks like Government Ministries wish to Divide and Rule using Gender Politics with everything coming down to Women Vote Banks and Money Making Businesses. Women's ministry receives more than Rs 50,000+ Crore grants from the Government but there is no proof that even 10% is utilized for Women's Empowerment. As per some prevalent conspiracy theories in fact a big chunk of the money may be ending up as party funds or even in some ministerial account. The question that needs to be asked and answered is that when 95% tax payers are Men and 95% Men work hard, struggle and die early to fulfill the needs of their families, why is there not even a single Scheme or Plan or any Support whatsoever for Men in India then?

Legal System Vs. Men

Government of India has enacted various one sided and biased laws against men and favoring only Women. Unlike above mentioned Schemes for Women, there is not a single scheme to support Men nor any law to protect Men in India. Men who had become trapped in the justice system have experienced severe social, economic, cultural and political disadvantages. Accordingly, these determinants of wellbeing are considered in order to provide a greater understanding of the factors which have permeated and shaped their lived experiences.

Men's experiences from their initial engagement with the police, then their experiences with lawyers, through to orders passed by Courts, clearly reveal that there exist strong perceptions of unconscious bias, unjust practices and an unholy

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nexus between feminists mafia, Police and Lawyers which the Government has not made any effort to address so far.

The use of legal terminology, the range of legal options made available to clients, and lawyers' willingness or lack thereof to defend non-guilty pleas has created barriers in the pursuit of justice for these men. When an individual is arrested for an alleged crime and subsequently tarred with a criminal record, there are long-term effects which may persist lifelong despite the individual getting bail or being acquitted from criminal charges. This is commonly referred to as the 'collateral consequences of conviction' which have a variety of impacts. Whilst this has broader socio-economic consequences, the stigma of having a criminal record provokes wide-ranging and subtle forms of discrimination and embarrassment. Once someone has been tagged as a criminal, it is almost impossible to get rid of the label; the public is easily persuaded that once a man is jailed, he must be a hardened criminal and must therefore be segregated and excluded from the rest. The inability of men to access quality legal services can generate, and/or perpetuate, social exclusion for individuals, especially when they are unaware of their legal rights. This is driven by a dominant discourse within the criminal justice system underpinned by the notion of Article 14 of the Constitution of India which says '*All are equal In front of law*'.

A woman who killed her husband has been freed of murder charges by the Supreme Court on the grounds that the husband had called her a prostitute and that this amounted to "sudden and grave provocation" which led to his killing in a fit of rage (NAWAZ Vs. THE STATE REP. BY INSPECTOR OF POLICE). Question is if man do same thing will honourable Supreme Court pardon?

One-night stand in an excusable situation not adultery: Gujarat HC (Sharmilaben vs. Pravinsinh Balvantsinh Solanki)

Such decisions leave one with no option other than to conclude that there exist unfortunate patterns of unconscious/conscious bias against Men in the Indian Justice System.

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Some of the most compelling scientific evidence proves that women are no less violent than men. But it has been seen that women's groups have threatened and bullied researchers or media or law enforcement agencies even Judges by any means possible to stop them from presenting evidence of the tendencies of women to engage as much as men, in the perpetration of domestic violence, and additionally to file false reports of sexual harassment, rape or abuse.

As an example, there is the case of a Judge who in his judgement had declared the IPC Section 498A as a tool of legal terrorism. Women's groups protested this judgement and broke several pieces of furniture and damaged public property in the court room.

Crime prevention is critical to maintain law and order in the country. National Crime Records Bureau mentions deterring criminals through deployment of more police force is one of the major strategies practiced. It also mentions reasons such as unemployment, poverty, a lower per capita income affects the crime rates in India.

The Government however has never tried to curtail crime by providing basic needs like education, training, spreading awareness of Law and ensuring guaranteed employment.

Opportunities for men to earn decently are almost nil in the country. In the name of gender upliftment, government has been completely biased in the appeasement of women and mostly one particular sector of women.

It should not come as a surprise to check the below statistics for the arrests and the gender ratio. There are many poorly drafted Acts and amendments to IPC that define the perpetrator as only a Man. And a significant percentage of fake cases too contribute to these high figures of arrests of Men.

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Unlike the Schemes created for the welfare of only women, there is not even a single Law or Act to protect vulnerable men from crime. Below listed Laws made only for women, and none for men and almost all of them are misused by women to make money or to control men.

1. Maternity Benefit Act,1861
2. Special Marriage Act, 1954
3. The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956
4. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961
5. Indian Divorce Act, 1969
6. Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act,1971
7. Equal Remuneration Act, 1976
8. The Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986
9. The Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987
10. National Commission for Women Act, 1990
11. Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005
12. The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006
13. Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013
14. Nirbhaya Act.
15. Disha Act.

With above listed laws, only women can complain against Men and in most of the complaints there is no need to provide any proof for the allegation, only sob story is enough to send a man and his family behind bars. In all the cases, the Burden of proof lies on Men to prove himself innocent.

Most of the crimes could be prevented with better policies, employment opportunities and widespread awareness of law. This would help counter the petty crimes to a major extent but Government of India is turning a blind eye to the acute need to protect and support men in distress. When it comes to police custody again men are at a disadvantage as no policeman/woman in his or her

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right senses would dare lift a finger against any woman considering the multitude of woman centric laws, acts and regulations that protect women. Unfortunately the same cannot be said to extend to men who can be treated like animals without any fear of repercussion thanks to the total lack of any legislation aimed specifically at protecting men. The most recent example occurred recently when a father-son duo were tortured, brutalized and murdered in a police station and it was only after a public outcry that action was taken against the culprits. Is it surprising then that given such wide ranging systemic discrimination against men and abuse of men, that a lot of men feel that they have no option left than to end their own life.

Government of India is over enthusiastic to buy into the worldwide feminist ideology. But feminism disguised as women empowerment is causing severe damage to the unifying fabric of cultural, family and spiritual values that defines this nation. The core mindset of the Government is misandrist which is clearly visible in the lack of support and help offered to Men in distress. Men are left out in the cold with no Law to take recourse to when victimized and are therefore more commonly resorting to suicides. The rate of Men's suicide in India is alarming with male deaths from suicides being nearly double that of females thanks to rising numbers of fake cases, ill treatment by society and total neglect by the Government.

As per the statistics, India has around 3.3 Crore people who pay tax and out of them 95% are men who work hard, struggle and even risk early deaths to satisfy the needs of their families but there is not even a single Scheme exclusively for men. 95% men work hard and pay taxes for the nation to run, but it is a shame to say that there are:

- No Laws to safeguard Men in the country
- No recovery or rehabilitation centres only for Men
- No recent Acts to look after the physical, economic and family welfare of Men

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- No data capture or analysis to research the actual crime rates against Men
- No small-scale economic opportunities
- No one-stop centres to guide or train Boys and Men for proper employment
- No research on the needs and support required for Boys and Men.

A National Men's commission is the most critical need of Indian Men today.

BIAS BY BIRTH

Male-perpetrated violence against women is taken much more seriously than female-perpetrated violence against men due to real or perceived physical strength differences between women and men.

The feminist argue and claim the notion that domestic violence is primarily a culturally supported male enterprise and that female violence is always defensive and reactive. When women are instigators, in this view, it is a “pre-emptive strike”, aimed at defending against an inevitable male attack. In contrast, violence against males is not similarly contextualized and is always attributed to a broader social agenda. As a result of this perspective, feminists tend to generalize about violent men and about all men while completely ignoring the female pathology.

There are strong social prohibitions inhibiting men from being aggressive against women and harsh legal sanctions facing men who dare to transgress but rarely any social prohibitions or legal sanctions inhibiting women from being aggressive against men - that is the reason why it is often said that it's a crime being a Male or to be born as a Male Child in India.

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DISCRIMINATION IN JOB SELECTION:

Men are more likely to face gender discrimination when applying for jobs than women, consistent with various studies done with around 1000 job applicants.

Research by the sociologist, examined how job applicants treated differently by employers supported their gender with an equivalent qualifications and experience.

In white-collar job employers in several occupational classes unevenly discriminate against men during early hiring practices. Hiring practices among employers across two gendered occupational dimensions:

- (1) Sex composition (male- or female-dominated jobs) and
- (2) Gender stereotyping (masculinized or feminized jobs).

Broadly, findings suggest a polarization of early sorting mechanisms during which discrimination against female applicants is concentrated in male-dominated and masculinized working-class jobs, whereas discrimination against male applicants at early job-access points is more widespread, occurring in women dominated and feminized jobs in both white-collar and working-class contexts. Interestingly, discrimination further compounds for male and feminine applicants—depending on the classed context—when these occupational dimensions align within the same gendered direction (e.g., male-dominated jobs that even have masculinized job advertisements). These findings have implications for the study of gender and

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work inequality and indicate the importance of a multidimensional approach to hiring-related inequality.

It is generally assumed that sex/gender discrimination are some things that only happens to women, but the research found that men face more discrimination when applying for jobs that are commonly related to the other sex.

Overall research found that men were more likely to be overlooked by employers supported their gender for both white-collar and working-class jobs. Women were also subject to discrimination when applying for working-class jobs because of their physical strength, but not white-collar jobs. This shows actual real statistics of discrimination against men

Gender discrimination was examined by first identifying whether employment advert involved stereotypically masculine traits, stereotypically feminine traits or was gender neutral. Their research measured whether this translated into a preference for male or female candidates, regardless of whether the work was during a male dominated or female dominated field.

Traits defined as stereotypically masculine included: physical strength; technical aptitude; leadership; independence; analytical thinking; assertiveness and ambition.

Traits defined as stereotypically feminine included: friendly; organized; team orientated and good communication skills.

Sex/gender discrimination was measured by counting what percentage male and feminine candidates received a positive callback from the employer, which in most cases meant being invited to an interview.

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Phone: +91-9972718212 / +91-9900954101

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Even there are reports of misuse of Sexual harassment at work place by women, still many corporates managed by men appoint women over men for white-collar jobs.

The study concluded that women applying for working-class jobs faced less discrimination in male-dominated roles, because of various types of schemes and reservation quota for women. But men within the study faced discrimination in female-dominated roles in both working-class and middle-class contexts, particularly when employers specified a preference for candidates with feminine traits and jobs specially reserved for women. Here is a latest AD from India's largest Group Companies The TATA's

TATA Industries - Hosur, Tamil Nadu needs Assembly Line & CNC Operators - 3000 Members.

Only for girls with stipend ranging from Rs. 15,000/- to 20,000/-

Qualification: +2 /ITI / Diploma - Any Stream.

Age: Girls between 18 - 22 Years

One month free training at NTTF - Vellore.

Then to Tata Factory after Training.

Free Jobs, Training, Food and Accommodation during training.

Contact 0416 - 2244017 or send an eMail to banuprasads@nttf.co.in for more details.
should apply before 30th October 2020.

TITAN-TIDCO Venture under the Tata Electronics

CONCLUSION:

Feminist research, feminist advocacy, and public debate so far have paid very little attention to the problems of gender bias and gender constructions in laws in general when it comes to Men which proves that such organizations are least interested in true gender equality.

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Criminal laws must emphasize that violence and harm against other people is morally wrong and that domestic violence is not a shameful private matter but a societal as well as individual injustice.

One-sided governmental policies that fund women-only resources, based on the assumption that women rarely, or never, engage as perpetrators of domestic violence, lie at the heart of the problem. Primary prevention efforts to curb domestic violence rather than focusing on male violence alone, even assaults by women on their male partners should be paid as much attention as possible.

Priority needs to be assigned to the victims of domestic violence, regardless of gender, particularly given the fact that men can also be victimized brutally, suffer serious financial hardship and are no less required to visit physicians or take time off from work or seek urgent counselling following any victimization.

That victimization experiences of men are downplayed as compared to those of women is discriminatory and should never be allowed. Domestic violence must be viewed not through the prism of gender but instead be considered as an issue that may be encountered by any human being regardless of gender.

Suffering due to atrocities and without legal recourse an abused man may as a last resort commit serious crimes or even commit suicide. This may be seen in some cases:

Article 14 of the Constitution of India reads as under: **Equality before law** - *"The State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India"* (Ref: <https://mynation.net/laws/coi/coi.htm>)

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Article 15 of the Constitution of India reads as under: *“Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth.”*

But same Article 15 of the Constitution of India contradict with clause 3 of Article 15, which reads as *“Nothing in this article shall prevent the State from making any special provision for women and children.”*

This shows systematic bias against Men, overriding 'Equality before Law' and 'Discrimination on grounds of Gender' Articles. If so why to add clause in Article 14 - **Equality before law** and **discrimination on grounds of Sex** in Article 15? Same can be drafted in simple way saying **MEN ARE NOT EQUAL TO WOMEN AND THEY ARE DISCRIMINATED BECAUSE OF THEIR GENDER/SEX.**

Not only men are discriminated because of their gender but most of Women centric laws reflect only one aspect about men i.e., *“Guilty until proven innocent”*

All of the above mentioned causes as well as Society, Spouse and System push men to take drastic steps finally leading to them to end of their own dear lives. Feminist mafia, prejudiced Indian society, one-sided media, bias from birth, and gynocentric, short-sighted Government Policies that completely neglect men are the main reasons which are responsible to cut short men’s life.

Worldwide around 800,000 people die due to suicide yearly, that’s one person every 40 seconds. Of these 1,39,123 (18%) are residents of India. 70% of suicides are by men and is mostly due to depression because of marital discord, which is responsible for their death. The overall male to female ratio of suicide victims for the year 2019 was 70.2: 29.8, which is more as compared to the year 2018 (68.5: 31.5). Globally, the suicide rate for men is twice than of women, that’s 13.9 per 100,000 for men and 6.3 per 100,000 for women. (Ref: MEN’S LIVES MATTERS – SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN’S HEALTH - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4649599>)

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All the above statistics show why men are committing suicide. Most of the suicides are because of family problems, threats from wives to file fake cases, financial commitment towards the family, one sided laws, Reservation and Schemes meant only for females, zero support from government, zero protection from current laws against false accusations and fake cases.

Men are abused, vilified, exploited and are expected to suffer in silence while women on the other hand are treasured, protected and pampered. Every country in the world, and the governments are pushing agendas for women's empowerment making special provisions for women's reservations / schemes / funding and enacting gender biased laws in favour of women. More MEN are suffering at the hands of an abusive female – wife / girlfriend / live-in partner which leads to depression and suicide. Yet strangely enough, hardly any studies have ever been conducted to research the psychological trauma that men have to face. Truly men today are under attack from all sides and the day is not far when to be born as a male will be considered the biggest curse and liability.

Every aspect of above details depicts biasness and discrimination towards male child even before birth. Today's generation opt for female child over male child for gender selection. As, there are many schemes and reservation only for girl child (e.g.: BETI BACHAO / SAVE THE GIRL CHILD) and not a single Reservation and quota system in Education, jobs, travel etc. for male child. All this displays SYSTEMATIC DISCRIMINATION towards Men, its really BIAS BY BIRTH. Being MAN is more of a SIN rather than a SHAME in today's World, especially in India.

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Reference:

Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health -
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4431600>

STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON
MEN'S HEALTH - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603151>

Violence Against Men – False Accusation of Sexual Harassment -
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4445147>

CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>

MEN'S LIVES MATTERS – SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH -
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4649599>

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